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NAUTILOS - New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean observation is an H2020 project funded under the Future of Seas and Oceans Flagship Initiative, coordinated by the National Research Council of Italy (CNR, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche). It brings together a group of 21 entities from 11 European countries with multidisciplinary expertise ranging from ocean instrumentation development and integration, ocean sensing and sampling instrumentation, data processing, modelling and control, operational oceanography and biology and ecosystems and biogeochemistry such, water and climate change science, technological marine applications, and research infrastructures.

NAUTILOS will fill-in marine observation and modelling gaps for chemical, biological and deep ocean physics variables through the development of a new generation of cost-effective sensors and samplers, the integration of the aforementioned technologies within observing platforms and their deployment in large-scale demonstrations in European seas. The fundamental aim of the project will be to complement and expand current European observation tools and services, to obtain a collection of data at a much higher spatial resolution, temporal regularity, and length than currently available at the European scale, and to further enable and democratise the monitoring of the marine environment to both traditional and non-traditional data users.

NAUTILOS is one of two projects included in the EU's efforts to support of the European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy by supporting the demonstration of new and innovative technologies to measure the Essential Ocean Variables (EOV).

More information on the project can be found at: <http://www.nautilus-h2020.eu>.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable reports the activities developed within task 9.2, focusing on the analysis of biogeochemical ocean forecasting improvements which may result from larger numbers of NAUTILOS-like observations being assimilated into the underlying physical models which drive these systems. Two different study sites were used, with different geographical scales and ocean dynamics: The Mediterranean Sea and the Hardanger Fjord coastal system. This diversity assures generality of the results and conclusions obtained.

Through an application of the OSSE method the results show that the improved physical solution from an increased number of assimilated observations also improves a biogeochemical model driven by a physical model. This is primarily through the improved representation of the nutrient cycling from a more accurate representation of the vertical structure of the water column, though they also improve the advective processes acting on plankton. As the biogeochemical processes are a downstream and non-linear consequence of the physics, the improvements were found to vary spatially and not equally to all compartments of the biogeochemical system.

Biogeochemical observations were used for calibration of the model system which is another path for utility of NAUTILOS derived observations, as demonstrated within the case studies. It would also be possible to assimilate the biogeochemical variables directly into the models which would likely improve the systems further, but this was beyond the scope of the modelling here.

These conclusions show that adoption of NAUTILOS technologies has the potential to improve biogeochemical forecast models. The vertical structure of the water column is of most importance for this highlighting the importance of profile measurements, for example from autonomous vehicles. The models can also be improved by improving the calibration of model parameters by using novel sensors or increased coverage to fill in gaps in current biogeochemical observations.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
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NAUTILOS	New Approach to Underwater Technologies for Innovative, Low-cost Ocean obServation
OSSE	Observing System Simulation Experiment
NR	Nature Run
FM	Forecast Model
AM	Assimilation Model
OBC	Open Boundary Conditions
netPP	Net primary production
POC	Particulate Organic Carbon
TEM	Temperature
SAL	Salinity
SSH	Sea surface height
SST	Sea surface temperature
ERSEM	European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model

I. INTRODUCTION

Deliverable D9.2 describes the activities carried out in WP9 Task 9.2 on the development and implementation of coupled hydrodynamic/biogeochemical models to investigate how new data made available by NAUTILOS can enhance the accuracy of the three-dimensional representation of biogeochemical structure and status of the ocean. An important part of Task 9.2 was to assess how NAUTILOS-like observations can improve the biogeochemical model skill, in relation to different variables. Two coupled models covering different marine environments and scales were adapted for this purpose: a basin-scale model for the Mediterranean Sea and a regional/local model for the Hardangerfjord in Norway.

The Mediterranean pelagic ecosystem may be considered as oligotrophic, exhibiting a well-defined eastward decreasing gradient in plankton productivity (Moutin and Raimbault, 2002; Kalaroni et al., 2020). This is largely related with the anti-estuarine circulation, with inflowing nutrient poor surface Atlantic water and outflowing subsurface Mediterranean waters. The primary production is mainly controlled by vertical mixing processes that supply the euphotic zone with deep water nutrients, reaching its maximum between December and April. The seasonal cycle is stronger in areas characterized by deep water formation, such as the Gulf of Lions in the northwestern Mediterranean. Relatively increased productivity is also found in areas receiving river nutrient inputs, such as the Northern Adriatic, the North Aegean, and the Gulf of Lions.

The Hardanger fjord is an estuarine system on the west coast of Norway characterised by deep branching fjords which flow out into a narrow shelf sea. At 180 km long it is the second longest fjord in Norway, it has several sills and basins within that length and branches considerably towards the coast, with branches connected by narrow tidal channels which can produce strong currents locally. Several large rivers run into the fjord making it semi-brackish in its upper reaches. The region is generally nutrient limited and the dynamics of blooms are controlled by the light limitation during periods of significant run off (snow melt) and the upwelling of nutrients on the shelf.

The following sections describe the methodologies applied for each of the two pilot sites, followed by the results of the simulations and a discussion of the main findings in relation to the objectives of the NAUTILOS project.

II. METHODOLOGY

MEDITERRANEAN

A three-dimensional coupled hydrodynamic/biogeochemical model is implemented at Mediterranean basin scale ($1/10^\circ$ resolution $\sim 10\text{km}$), based on the currently operational model within POSEIDON forecasting system (www.poseidon.hcmr.gr; Korres et al., 2007; Kalaroni et al., 2020a, b). The hydrodynamic model is based on the Princeton Ocean Model (POM, Blumberg and Mellor, 1983), which is a three-dimensional, sigma-coordinate and free surface primitive equation model. The model prognostic variables are temperature, salinity, velocity, sea surface height and turbulent kinetic energy. The biogeochemical model is based on the European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model (ERSEM; Baretta et al., 1995) that follows a “functional” group approach, including four phytoplankton groups (diatoms, nanoplankton, picoplankton, dinoflagellates), three zooplankton groups (heterotrophic nanoflagellates microzooplankton, mesozooplankton) and bacteria. The pelagic model variables also include particulate and dissolved organic matter, along with dissolved inorganic nutrients (nitrate, ammonium, phosphate, silicate). The chemical dynamics of nitrogen, phosphorus, silicate and oxygen are coupled with the biologically driven carbon dynamics, as each group has dynamically varying C:N:P ratios. The benthic-pelagic coupling is described by a simple first-order benthic return module, describing the settling of organic detritus and diffusional nutrient fluxes out of the sediment. The hydrodynamic/biogeochemical model POM-ERSEM has also been coupled to a carbonate system sub-model (Blackford and Gilbert, 2007), which uses the HALTAFALL (Ingri et al., 1967) carbonate speciation code to calculate the CO_2 partial pressure (pCO_2), pH and carbonate system components (H_2CO_3 , HCO_3^- , CO_3^{2-}) in the water column, using dissolved inorganic carbon (DIC) and total alkalinity (TA) as input. The air-sea CO_2 flux, quantifying the CO_2 ocean uptake, which is important for climate studies, can be also calculated as $\text{CO}_2 \text{ air-sea flux} = k \cdot H \cdot [\text{pCO}_2^{\text{air}} - \text{pCO}_2^{\text{water}}]$, with k being a function of temperature, related with water pCO_2 solubility and H a semi-empirical function of wind speed.

Figure 1 - Mediterranean Sea model domain and bathymetry (m).

Along with the operational ($1/10^\circ$ resolution $\sim 10\text{km}$, MED10) model, a finer resolution ($1/20^\circ \times 1/20^\circ$, $\sim 5 \text{ km}$) basin-scale coupled hydrodynamic/biogeochemical model (MED20) was also set up. The initial hydrodynamic/biogeochemical 3-D fields for MED20 were obtained from

MED10 with bi-linear interpolation. After a 5-year spin-up (2010-2014), MED20 was re-initialized and a hindcast simulation was performed over 2010. Following the concept of the Observing Systems Simulation Experiments (OSSE) implemented within NAUTILOS project (see Deliverables D8.6 and D9.1), additional simulations were performed with the coarser resolution coupled model ($1/10^\circ \times 1/10^\circ$, ~ 10 km) MED10, to evaluate the benefit from assimilating new NAUTILOS-like “synthetic” observations (temperature/salinity profiles and sea surface height/temperature) on the biogeochemical model skill. In this context, the “synthetic” observations were obtained from the fine resolution MED20 hydrodynamic model hindcast simulation, being considered as the Nature Run (NR). The simulated distribution of biogeochemical variables with the MED10 coupled model was evaluated against MED20 distributions, being considered as the “truth”. All experiments were performed for the 2010 period.

The OSSE simulations performed with the coarse resolution model (MED10) included:

- a) Free model run (FM) without any data assimilation applied,
- b) Assimilation of 78 randomly selected temperature (TEM)/salinity (SAL) profiles (AM_{r78} , see Figure 2), corresponding to the pre-NAUTILOS ocean observation status, and
- c) Assimilation of 110 randomly selected TEM/SAL profiles (AM_{r110} , see Figure 2), corresponding to the post-NAUTILOS ocean observations implying a 40% increase in the ocean observations.
- d) Assimilation of 110 TEM/SAL profiles (AM_{opt110} , see Figure 2), selected based on a semi-empirical algorithm, which was used to identify locations with stronger model improvement (see Deliverable 9.1).
- e) Assimilation of TEM/SAL profiles (AM_{all}) from the NR for every grid point location.

In all assimilating runs, along with TEM/SAL profiles, sea surface height (SSH) and sea surface temperature (SST) surface data for the entire model grid were assimilated from the NR, representing currently available satellite products.

Figure 2 - Annual sea surface height (SSH, m) and sea surface temperature (SST, °C), simulated with MED20 nature run (NR) and MED10 free run (FM), assimilating 78 (AM_{r78}) and 110 (AM_{r110}) randomly selected and 110 optimally selected (AM_{opt110}) TEM/SAL profiles, along with SSH/SST surface data. Assimilated TEM/SAL profiles locations in AM_{r78}, AM_{r110} and AM_{opt110} simulations are indicated by black dots.

To assess the environmental status at a local scale, the coupled model was also downscaled with higher-resolution ($1/120^\circ \times 1/120^\circ$, ~ 800 m) in Saronikos Gulf, a region characterized by significant aquaculture activity (see Figure 3). Indicative simulations were carried out using this fine-resolution coastal model to evaluate the added value of improved open boundary conditions (OBC), derived from basin-scale OSSE simulations. In this framework, the coastal simulation forced with OBC from the high-resolution MED20 model served as the "Nature Run" and was compared against coastal simulations using OBC derived from the MED10 OSSE experiments, which assimilated SSH/SST and 110 TEM/SAL profiles—distributed either uniformly scattered (AM_{s110}) or optimally selected (AM_{opt110}) as described before. This approach allowed for assessing the impact of enhanced basin-scale hydrodynamic representation on the biogeochemical conditions of the coastal subregion, even though no profiles were directly assimilated within the Saronikos Gulf.

Figure 3 - Annual mean sea surface height (SSH, m) and circulation patterns in the northeastern Mediterranean (left), simulated with MED20 Nature Run; and the locations of shellfish and finfish aquaculture farms in the Saronikos Gulf (right; corresponding area highlighted with a blue box on the left), according to EMODnet (emodnet.ec.europa.eu).

HARDANGER FJORD SYSTEM

NIVA utilized hydro-physical data derived from the Nature Run (NR) simulation in Task D8.2, alongside OSSE solutions from Task D9.1, to run a coupled pelagic-biogeochemical model for both a Nature Run, and runs representing assimilation of data pre implementation of NAUTILOS sensors and post-NAUTILOS sensors. The hydrodynamic model used was Regional Ocean Modeling System (ROMS) and was run on a 160m resolution grid for the nature run and 800m resolution for the assimilative runs, with both grids covering the same area of the Hardanger fjord and adjacent shelf (Figure 4). The biogeochemical model used was the European Regional Seas Ecosystem Model (ERSEM, Butenschon et al. 2016) as described above with some adaptations specifically for the western Norway region. ERSEM is a variable stoichiometry biogeochemical model representing the planktonic food web, microbial loop, nutrients, oxygen, carbonate chemistry, and a simple benthic model. The adaptations from standard ERSEM which are used here, are an expanded plankton set (to include prymnesiophytes which are common in this area and mixotrophs) and the splitting of the DOM into coloured and non-coloured portions to accurately represent the river run off. Boundary conditions for the biogeochemical variables are taken from the CMEMS global biogeochemistry model (retrieved from Copernicus Marine Service, <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00015>) and river inputs are derived from a land run off model.

The biogeochemical framework of the model is particularly well-suited for predicting climate change impacts on marine ecosystems, focusing on essential ocean variables that reflect ecosystem status and health, such as oxygen levels, pH, CO₂ concentrations, nutrients, and phytoplankton biomass.

ERSEM when coupled with ROMS has to be run online (that is solving both the physics and biogeochemistry at the same time). The number of state variables included in ERSEM and the availability of the computing system however made it infeasible to run on the 160m resolution model natively with both the hydrodynamics and biogeochemistry. Furthermore, the complications of running the assimilation scheme for the OSSE experiments, and the

need to test multiple different setups (whilst only assimilating physics variables) along with the potential instabilities from running the coupled biogeochemistry at a longer timestep, made it undesirable to run the coupled physics-biogeochemistry directly with the assimilative system.

We therefore implemented a method which restarted the coupled physics-biogeochemical model each day on the 800m resolution grid maintaining the biogeochemistry variables but overwriting the physics from a saved forcing run (the 160m ROMS run interpolated to the 800m grid in the case of the nature run, and the pre- and post-Nautilus assimilation runs already on the 800m grid for the OSSE experiments). In this manner the physics is repeatedly nudged back towards the higher resolution or assimilative run whilst the biogeochemistry was carried over to be a continuous run. Given the timescales of the biogeochemical processes are in general longer than the physics, this gives output where the but without the computational expense of running the higher resolution grid/assimilation coupled directly to the biogeochemistry. Even with this system in place the limited data available from the assimilative runs (see D9.1) meant that the comparison period is one spring period. This is the most dynamic period for the ecosystem and should therefore represent the period of greatest impact.

The runs compared are then all on the 800m grid and comprise:

- A) Nature run, forced by ROHO160 high resolution physics
- B) Pre-Nautilus, forced by ROHO800 assimilating data at two existing mooring stations
- C) Post-Nautilus, forced by ROHO800 assimilating data at aquaculture sites within the Hardangerfjord system

Figure 4 - Extent of the ROHO grids and the assimilation points used in the post-Nautilus model.

III. SIMULATIONS RESULTS

MEDITERRANEAN

The biogeochemical model parameterization was slightly modified to obtain a better fit with available in situ data. In particular, the light attenuation coefficient was obtained from satellite derived diffuse attenuation coefficient (GlobColour KD490, Lee et al., 2005), instead of being calculated as a function of (model simulated) particulate organic matter. This results in a more realistic simulation of deep Chl-a maximum, particularly in the more oligotrophic Eastern Mediterranean, as compared with Medatlas in situ data climatology (www.ncei.noaa.gov/archive/accession/0000996) (see Figure 5). Moreover, the phytoplankton affinity parameter, related with dissolved inorganic nutrients maximum uptake rate, was increased, in order to obtain a better fit with observed (lower) concentrations of nutrients at Cretan Sea and Ligurian Sea (see Figure 6).

Figure 5 - Mean summer Chl-a (mg/m³), transect in the Eastern (left, Latitude=34oN) and Western (left, Latitude=42oN) Mediterranean, simulated with the satellite derived attenuation coefficient (Model New, middle) and the old model parameterization (Model Old, bottom), against Medatlas climatology (top).

Figure 6 - Surface nitrate (mmol/m^3 , top) and phosphate (mmol/m^3 , bottom), simulated with the increased nutrient uptake rate (new, black line) and the old parameterization (old, red line) summer Chl- a (mg/m^3) at DYFAMED (7.9°E , 43.3°N , Ligurian Sea) and HCB (35.43°N , 25.07°E , Cretan Sea) sites, against in situ data (data.emso.eu).

Figure 7 - Seasonally mean (2013-2014) near surface Chl- a (mg/m^3), simulated with the coarse (MED10, left) and fine (MED20, middle) resolution model, against GlobColour satellite Chl- a (right).

The simulated Chl- a with the fine (MED20) and coarse (MED10) resolution coupled models is compared in Figure 7 against GlobColour satellite Chl- a (www.globcolour.info), showing reasonable agreement in capturing the observed spatial and seasonal variability, characterized by relatively higher Chl- a concentrations in the Western Mediterranean and in areas (e.g. Alboran Sea, N. Aegean, N. Adriatic) receiving important lateral nutrient inputs (rivers runoff, Black Sea Water, Atlantic Water). The simulated seasonal cycle is, in agreement with observations, characterized by higher Chl- a during autumn-winter period, due to stronger vertical mixing and lower during more stratified spring-summer period, as water stratification prevents the nutrient supply from deeper layers. The model tends to overestimate Chl- a in the Eastern basin during autumn-winter period and underestimate Chl- a concentration in the Northwestern Mediterranean during winter-spring period, which is

mostly related to the hydrodynamic model underestimation/overestimation of the mixing intensity, affecting phytoplankton bloom dynamics (Kalaroni et al., 2020a).

The spatial variability of $p\text{CO}_2$ and CO_2 air-sea flux (Figure 8) is mainly controlled by temperature and primary production, the latter showing an eastward decreasing gradient, opposite with temperature (i.e., increases eastward). A significant part of the $p\text{CO}_2$ and CO_2 air-sea flux spatial variability is related to the dependence of $p\text{CO}_2$ solubility on the water temperature (i.e., decrease of solubility with increasing temperature). Thus, $p\text{CO}_2$ follows an eastward increasing gradient, being higher in the Eastern Mediterranean. Moreover, in open sea areas, lower temperature is indicative of deeper winter mixing (e.g., Gulf of Lions, Southern Adriatic, North Aegean), resulting in an overall higher primary production and CO_2 net biological uptake. Overall, at basin-scale, the concurrent variability of temperature and productivity results in a significant correlation ($r=-0.82$) between CO_2 air-sea flux and temperature.

Figure 8 - Annual mean CO_2 air-sea flux ($\text{mmol}/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$, top left), SST ($^{\circ}\text{C}$, bottom left), surface $p\text{CO}_2$ (μatm , top right) and net primary production ($\text{mgC}/\text{m}^3/\text{day}$, bottom right), simulated with MED20 model. Positive CO_2 air-sea flux indicates net CO_2 ocean uptake.

In Figures 9-12 the OSSE simulations (see above methodology section), performed with the coarser resolution (MED10) model, are compared against the NR (considered as the “truth”) for different variables to evaluate the impact of hydrodynamics and also the benefit from assimilating NAUTILOS-like “synthetic” observations (temperature/salinity profiles and sea surface height/temperature) in the biogeochemical model skill. The pelagic ecosystem seasonal dynamics is primarily driven by vertical mixing, which results in the entrainment of dissolved inorganic nutrients from deeper layers, enhancing phytoplankton productivity in the euphotic layer. Thus, the main impact of hydrodynamics, as illustrated by the differences between the NR and MED10 simulations for different biogeochemical variables (see Figures 10-12) is largely related with changes in vertical mixing (see Figure 9). For example, areas with relatively stronger vertical mixing in MED10 FM simulation (G. Lions and S. Adriatic dense water formation sites, Tyrrhenian Sea, Ionian Sea, see Figure 9) show also relatively higher phosphates concentration (see Figure 10). Given that dissolved inorganic nutrients are the

main driver of the pelagic plankton ecosystem, similar patterns may be seen also for Chl-a (Figure 11) and subsequently for mesozooplankton (Figure 12) distributions, with some exceptions being also noticed. For example, NR Chl-a (Figure 11) and mesozooplankton (Figure 12) present relatively higher concentration in the Tyrrhenian Sea, despite the relatively lower annual mean phosphates concentration (Figure 10), following the relatively weaker (winter) vertical mixing (Figure 9) in this area. This may be attributed to differences in near surface circulation (Figure 3), resulting in relatively higher PO_4 and Chl-a/mesozooplankton concentration during spring/summer period (not shown). Thus, near surface circulation and advection from ocean currents is another factor (yet less important) affecting the biogeochemical variables distributions, apart from vertical mixing. In the case of CO_2 air-sea flux (Figure 13), differences between NR and FM distributions are also related with temperature (Figure 3) that affects pCO_2 water solubility. Thus, the NR distribution is characterized by relatively higher CO_2 air-sea flux (i.e. lower water pCO_2) in the Eastern Mediterranean, as compared to the FM distribution, due to the relatively lower temperature (Figure 3) and slightly higher phytoplankton (i.e. higher CO_2 uptake, see Figure 11).

Figure 9 - Annual mean mixed layer depth (m), simulated with MED20 (Nature Run, top left) and MED10 free run (FM, top middle) and assimilating 78 (AM_{r78}, top right) and 110 (AM_{r110}, bottom left) randomly selected, 110 optimally selected (AM_{opt110}, bottom middle) and the entire grid (AM_{all}, bottom right) TEM/SAL profiles, along with SSH/SST surface data. Assimilated TEM/SAL profiles locations in AM_{r78}, AM_{r110} and AM_{opt110} simulations are indicated by black dots.

Figure 10 - As in Figure X.8 for annual mean surface phosphates (PO_4) concentration (mmol/m³).

Figure 11 - As in Figure X.8 for annual mean surface Chl-a concentration (mg/m3).

Figure 12 - As for X.7 for annual mean surface mesozooplankton biomass (mgC/m3).

Figure 13 - As for X.7 for annual mean CO2 air-sea flux (mmol/m2/day).

Differences from the NR are reduced when synthetic observations (TEM/SAL profiles and surface SSH/SST data) are assimilated in MED10 simulations, with AM_{all} (assimilation in all grid points) approaching the NR distributions in most cases. This is indicative of the important effect of hydrodynamics in driving the ecosystem. Even though the NR and FM have different biogeochemical initial conditions, these approach a similar annual mean distribution, when the FM hydrodynamics are strongly restored to those from NR in the AM_{all} simulation. Of course, there are still remaining important differences, which originate from non-linear effects and food-web interactions, triggered from the different hydrodynamics in the two

model simulations. Moreover, we should note that synthetic observations are assimilated with an 8-day frequency, allowing for the hydrodynamics in MED10 simulations to diverge from the NR conditions.

To evaluate the benefit from assimilating synthetic observations from the NR on the biogeochemical model skill, MED10 distributions for different variables are compared against the NR distributions (considered as the “truth”) in Figure 14 Taylor diagrams. As mentioned above, the AM_{all} simulation presents a clear improvement, over the Free run (FM) for all variables. In the case of phosphates, AM_{r78} and AM_{r110} also present an increasingly (in this order) improved skill over the free run (FM), which is consistent with the increasing number of observations (see also Table 1). AM_{opt110} represents an optimal choice of locations for assimilating (110) TEM/SAL profiles (see D9.1) and appears slightly better than the simulation with 110 random locations (AM_{r110}). The differences (i.e. correlation, RMSD) between all AM simulations, however, appear quite small. In the case of Chl-a, the skill of AM_{opt110} is slightly better than AM_{r78} , both lying between FM and AM_{all} , while AM_{r110} shows a slightly better skill than AM_{all} (see also Table 1). In the case of mesozooplankton, only AM_{all} appears better than FM, with other simulations ($AM_{r78} > AM_{opt110} > AM_{r110}$) being slightly worse than FM. Finally, in the case of CO_2 air-sea flux, the improvement in the model skill ($AM_{all} > AM_{r110} > AM_{opt110} > AM_{r78}$) is much more noticeable, with $AM_{r78}/AM_{r110}/AM_{opt110}$ showing a similar skill, between AM_{all} and FM. The important impact from assimilating TEM/SAL profiles on CO_2 air-sea flux may be largely attributed to the stronger effect of temperature, due to pCO_2 solubility temperature dependence.

Figure 14 - Taylor diagrams for surface phosphates (mmol/m³, top left), Chl-a (mg/m³, top right), mesozooplankton biomass (mgC/m³, bottom right) and CO₂ air-sea flux (mmol/m²/day, bottom left), simulated with MED10 free run (FM) and assimilating 78 (r78) and 110 (r110) randomly selected, 110 optimally selected (opt110) and the entire grid (all) TEM/SAL profiles, along with SSH/SST data, against NR.

Table 1 - Relative RMSD (RRMSD) decrease (%) in assimilation runs (AMr78, AMr110, AMopt110, AMall) compared to the free run ((AM/FM-1)*100) for different variables (PO₄, Chl-a, mesozooplankton, CO₂ air sea flux).

RRMSD (%) (AM/FM-1)*100	PO ₄	Chl-a	Mesozooplankton	CO ₂ air-sea flux
AM _{r78}	-2.6	-2.8	-3,9	-15.6
AM _{r110}	-3.2	-9.3	0,6	-17.6
AM _{opt110}	-3.4	-5.3	-1,5	-16.5
AM _{all}	-3.9	-6.6	-13,1	-27.0

Simulations with the downscaled higher-resolution model (1/120° × 1/120°, SAR120) in Saronikos Gulf, provide useful insights on the distribution of biogeochemical variables. The fine-resolution model presents a more detailed representation of the internal circulation within the Gulf, compared to the MED20 Nature Run (see Figure 15).

Figure 15 - Example comparison of sea surface height (SSH, m) between the MED20 Nature Run (right) and the higher-resolution downscaled SAR120 model (left) in the Saronikos Gulf region for the winter (Jan - Mar) 2010.

The performance of various OSSE experiments forced with OBC from the MED10 forecast model—including the free run (FM) and assimilation runs using SSH/SST and 110 TEM/SAL profiles from uniformly distributed (AM_{s110}) and optimally selected (AM_{opt110}) locations—is evaluated against the Nature Run (forced with OBC from the MED20 model) and presented in Figure 16. As observed previously, the assimilation models show clear improvements in the nutrient fields (e.g. phosphates), while phytoplankton biomass (i.e. Chl-a) and net primary production exhibit more variable or even opposite behaviour. Nonetheless, the positive impact of a more realistic representation of the OBC in the assimilation models is evident, particularly along the model boundaries and in the vertical structure of phosphates, as illustrated in Figure 17. Notably, the optimally selected assimilation run (AM_{opt110}) consistently outperformed the uniformly scattered configuration (AM_{s110}) across all evaluated metrics.

Figure 16 - Taylor diagrams for surface phosphates (mmol/m³, top left), Chl-a (mg/m³, top right), net primary production (mgC/m³/day, bottom left) and mesozooplankton biomass (mgC/m³, bottom right), of SAR120 model simulated with OBC from MED10 free run (FM) and assimilating 110 uniformly scattered (AM_{s110}) and optimally selected (AM_{opt110}) TEM/SAL profiles, along with SSH/SST data, against NR.

Figure 17 - Annual mean phosphates concentration (mg/m^3) of the whole domain (left) and RMSD values in the vertical profile from 0-100 m (right), simulated for Saronikos Gulf SAR120 model forced with OBC from MED20 (Nature Run, top left) and MED10 free run (FM, top right) and a 110 uniformly scattered (AM_{s110} , bottom left) and optimally selected (AM_{opt110} , bottom right) TEM/SAL profiles along with SSH/SST data.

HARDANGER FJORD SYSTEM

The biogeochemistry model was run being nudged to the physics from the Nature Run for one spring. This showed that, as expected, there is considerable control from the physics on the ecosystem, with nutrients being input from the rivers and upwelling from offshore (Figure 18). This creates a response from the phytoplankton growth along the coastal zone and within some fjord areas (Figure 19). There is also a high concentration on the southern boundary of the model which represents advection from the south, though the quantities may be artificially high from the adjustment between the (coarser resolution) boundary data and the internal model solution from this run. There is increased biomass of zooplankton in these areas (Figure 20) driven by grazing patterns, with bacteria also having a similar pattern (not shown). The particulate organic matter (POC) however shows much higher concentrations within the fjord system driven by the riverine input (Figure 21).

Figure 18 - Surface Nitrate in Nature run (end of run snapshot).

Figure 19 - Chl-a concentrations in Nature run (end of run snapshot).

Figure 20 - Zooplankton mass (carbon) concentration in the Nature run (end of run snapshot).

Figure 21 - POC concentration in Nature run (end of run snapshot).

We now look at the impact of the improved physics in the OSSE experiment. The assimilative runs were for 14 days. The Nature Run was spun up for 22 days before this and the assimilative runs started from the same initial state (interpolated from the CMEMS model also used for the boundary conditions, as would be the case in an operational system). This means pre- and post-Nautilos forced runs begin with the same error and we can see the errors evolve differently over time as the impact of the differing forcing physics exerts itself (Figure 22). There is a modest improvement in the error for all the components

of the biogeochemical system by the end of the run, however it takes some time for this to develop.

This reflects that the biogeochemical variables, whilst strongly controlled by the physics, are a downstream and non-linear response. The improvement in Chlorophyll can be seen only after day 10 when the nutrients are also improved. The large improvement in POC comes after the zooplankton from which a significant portion of pelagic POC is derived. This is where the improvement in POC error is concentrated despite the large inputs from the rivers.

Spatially the changes are concentrated within the fjord and coastal system, and have several small areas with especially large improvement (Figure 23). This reflects a combination of areas which are productive and where the vertical structure is improved. The changes are less widespread than observed in the physics (D9.1) however there are some changes throughout the domain. Especially at the open boundaries these vary between improved and degraded with the increased assimilation. Since the open boundary is far from the points where the assimilation is taking place this represents the overall solution adjusting the new information within the fjords but may be erroneous.

Figure 22 - Domain wide RMSE over time for pre- (blue) and post-Nautilus (orange) runs. Shown for the four variables in Figures 18-21.

The improvement in error is also summarised in Taylor diagrams (Figure 24) which shows that puts into context that whilst the improvements are positive, they are small.

Figure 23 - Change in RMSE for Chl-a between pre- and post-Nautilus runs (at last timestep). Blue indicates an improvement (reduction) in forecast error and red an degradation.

Figure 24 - Taylor diagrams comparing pre- and post-Nautilus data to the Nature run for the same four variables as Figure 22. Clockwise from top left – Nitrate, Chlorophyll, POC, Zooplankton.

IV. DISCUSSION

MEDITERRANEAN

A three-dimensional coupled hydrodynamic/biogeochemical model, based on the currently operational within POSEIDON system (www.poseidon.hcmr.gr; Korres et al., 2007; Kalaroni et al., 2020a, b), was implemented at Mediterranean basin scale. The biogeochemical model parameterization was slightly modified, with regard to light attenuation and phytoplankton nutrient uptake, to obtain a better fit with available in situ data. Along with the operational ($1/10^\circ$ resolution $\sim 10\text{km}$, MED10) model, a finer resolution ($1/20^\circ \times 1/20^\circ$, $\sim 5\text{ km}$, MED20) model was also set up. The latter was considered the Nature Run (NR), used to obtain “synthetic” observations (temperature/salinity profiles and sea surface height/temperature). A series of OSSE simulations were performed with the coarser resolution (MED10) model to evaluate the impact of hydrodynamics and also the benefit from assimilating NAUTILOS-like “synthetic” observations on the biogeochemical model skill. The simulated distribution of biogeochemical variables with the MED10 coupled model was evaluated against MED20 distributions, being considered as the “truth”. In the simulation AMall (assimilation in all grid points), MED10 distributions approached the NR distributions for all variables, which is indicative of the effect of hydrodynamics in driving the ecosystem. Considering also the other (more realistic) OSSE simulations (AM_{r78}, AM_{r110}, AM_{opt110}), dissolved inorganic nutrients presented a predictable behaviour, in response to the assimilation of synthetic observations, showing the expected improvement with increasing number of assimilated TEM/SAL profiles. This was to a point expected, as dissolved inorganic nutrients are directly affected by vertical mixing, while also fuelling plankton production and are thus a key link between hydrodynamics and ecosystem. Despite this, the relative RMSD decrease in AM simulations was quite small (see Table 1). This is probably related to the fast dynamics and small residence time of dissolved inorganic nutrients, being directly taken up by phytoplankton. Thus, other ecosystem components up the food chain, such as phytoplankton (taking up nutrients) and zooplankton (feeding on phytoplankton), showed a slightly stronger RMSD decrease, but at the same time, they showed an increasingly less predictable response to changing hydrodynamics, given the non-linear effects and complex food-web interactions. Finally, the improvement in the model skill from assimilating TEM/SAL profiles was much more noticeable on CO₂ air-sea flux, which is largely related to the stronger effect of temperature, given the pCO₂ solubility temperature dependence.

HARDANGER FJORD SYSTEM

An implementation of ROMS-ERSEM was run for a fjordic system on the west coast of Norway. The model system had not previously been run as a forecast or assimilative setup. As documented in D9.1 there was considerable trouble in achieving an assimilative scheme which improved the physics. The ERSEM model has a large number of state variables and to make the OSSE experiment feasible when the coupled system has to be run online (meaning the physics and biogeochemistry being calculated at the same time) within the computing resource available a system was setup which nudged the physics back to the assimilative solution at the start of each day whilst carrying over the state of the biogeochemical system.

The Nature run was forced by a higher resolution physics model (160m compared to 800m) but calculated on the coarser 800m grid with the higher resolution physics interpolated.

Running this system for pre- and post-Nautilus assimilation setups there was an improvement in all the compartments of the biogeochemical system however it took ~10 days from starting the forecasts for the improvement to show. The time taken likely reflects several factors. One factor is the control from the physics is largely through the nutrients supply, but only some changes in the physics will directly impact this so, for example the vertical mixing and upwelling, therefore the assimilation will only improve the solution during these episodes. The daily restart system will also likely increase the length of time it takes for the improvement to be felt as the physics may 'drift' away from the improved solution between the daily updates. This system is however representative of a forecast system which has assimilation updated for its hindcast daily.

Spatially the improvements were generally concentrated within a few small areas. Although the synthetic observations were based on the idea of implementing opportunistic observation platforms at aquaculture sites, the number of such sites and their spread means additional observations were distributed fairly evenly throughout the fjord system. This means the spatial changes do not reflect the assimilation sites but two other factors; the areas of higher biological productivity where there is more scope for improvement and the areas where the vertical structure of the physics has more impact. Within a fjordic system there are features such as tidal jets which even if the representation is improved slightly will not significantly improve the biogeochemical results whereas other regions, such as fronts or upwelling zones, might yield significant improvements.

There was also evidence of small changes throughout the domain even out to the open boundaries which are far from any of the assimilation points. This reflects the complexity of adjusting an internal model solution to new data and is not unexpected but worth considering that assimilation may degrade the result in some areas of the domain, especially if a model has been heavily calibrated in an existing setup before the assimilation is added.

V. IMPACT OF NAUTILOS-LIKE OBSERVATIONS ON BIOGEOCHEMICAL OCEAN FORECASTING

A series of OSSE simulations were performed to evaluate the impact of improved hydrodynamics from assimilating NAUTILOS-like “synthetic” observations (temperature/salinity profiles, sea surface temperature/height) on the biogeochemical model skill. Two coupled hydrodynamic/biogeochemical models were implemented, covering two different marine environments and scales (Mediterranean basin-scale, Hardangerfjord coastal scale).

In the Mediterranean, dissolved inorganic nutrients presented a predictable behaviour, in response to the assimilation of synthetic observations (temperature/salinity profiles), showing an improved skill with a relatively higher amount (+40%) of post-NAUTILOS ocean observations. This predictable behaviour was largely attributed to the nutrients being directly affected by hydrodynamic processes (i.e. vertical mixing), acting as a link between hydrodynamics and plankton productivity. However, this skill improvement was quite small, which may be explained by their fast dynamics, being directly taken up by phytoplankton. The latter showed a relatively stronger skill improvement with additional observations, while components up the food chain, such as mesozooplankton, showed a less predictable response to changing hydrodynamics, given the non-linear effects and complex food-web interactions. The improvement in the model skill from assimilating TEM/SAL profiles was much more noticeable on CO₂ air-sea flux, which was largely related to the stronger effect of temperature, given the pCO₂ solubility temperature dependence.

In the Hardangerfjord the system also showed a skill improvement across the ecosystem components when assimilating the synthetic 'Nautilus' observations. These improvements took time to be apparent as the system evolved from the same starting point indicating that continuous observations are of most value when looking at downstream impacts, as the effect of improving the physics takes time to be translated into the biogeochemistry. The improvements were concentrated in a few regions as only some places have the intersection of importance for the ecosystem and physics where the vertical structure can be significantly improved by assimilation meaning additional observations were not equally valuable throughout the domain.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Hydrodynamics is an important driver of plankton productivity, particularly through vertical mixing, which controls the entrainment of nutrients from deeper layers, but also through advection by ocean currents, creating biological patches, fronts etc. Therefore, improving the hydrodynamics by assimilating satellite (sea surface temperature, sea surface height) products and other in situ (e.g. Argo floats, Ferrybox, aquaculture site) data will contribute to an improved skill of biogeochemical models. This is shown here for synthetic simulations of increased temperature, salinity, and sea surface height observations from Nautilus sensors. Using biogeochemical data from satellite products (e.g., ocean colour/chlorophyll-a, light attenuation) and in situ data (e.g., dissolved oxygen, inorganic nutrients, chlorophyll from platforms such as Ferrybox, BioArgo) for assimilation and/or parameter estimation, in combination with hydrodynamic data assimilation, is expected to further enhance the skill of biogeochemical models.

The overall improvement of the models due to the assimilation of additional data is expected to also positively impact nested coastal/regional scale models, even in areas without direct observational input, as demonstrated by the OSSE results in Saronikos Gulf, using improved open boundary conditions.

Despite the enhanced capacity for biogeochemical monitoring (e.g. BioArgo) there are still important gaps and limited data coverage for biogeochemical variables (e.g. nutrient profiles), particularly carbonate chemistry data (e.g. pCO₂, pH etc). Therefore, the anticipated increase of available biogeochemical data with new low-cost sensors developed within NAUTILOS is expected to be of significant value. Contribution from NAUTILOS cost-effective sensors can widen both the areas covered and, particularly important for biogeochemical variables, by extending coverage of the full seasonal cycle.

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